

Special Issue

Continuing Tradition? Sacralization Practices in the Early Islamicate West and the Influence of Late Antiquity

Message from the Guest Editors

The proposed volume will focus on social-cultural practices that were used to assert or increase the sacral significance of a particular space. The term practice is used here to refer to rituals, particularly the visual, audible and olfactory impact of these on their surroundings, and to the commemoration of persons and deeds through material culture, literature and liturgy. Rather than the legend, person or act to which the sacrality of a place is “attributed”, the articles in this volume will analyze what processes contributed to the creation of sacrality and how these invoked the attention of participants. The geographical scope will encompass urban spaces broadly within the Islamicate West. The historical focus will be the early Islamic period and the period of late Antiquity preceding and overlapping this. The purpose of this Special Issue is to bring new insights to the study of sacrality and topography by examining how the process of imbuing a space with religious significance interacted with existing memories of sacrality, as well as notions of divine choice that were associated specifically with the religious tradition in question.

Guest Editors

Dr. Javier Albarrán

Departamento de Historia Antigua, Medieval y Paleografía y
Diplomática, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, 28049 Madrid, Spain

Dr. Antonia Bosanquet

Faculty of Humanities, Asia-Africa-Institute, University of Hamburg,
20146 Hamburg, Germany

Deadline for manuscript submissions

closed (1 June 2023)

Religions

an Open Access Journal
by MDPI

Impact Factor 0.6
CiteScore 1.3

mdpi.com/si/127649

Religions
Editorial Office
MDPI, Grosspeteranlage 5
4052 Basel, Switzerland
Tel: +41 61 683 77 34
religions@mdpi.com

[mdpi.com/journal/
religions](https://mdpi.com/journal/religions)

Religions

an Open Access Journal
by MDPI

Impact Factor 0.6
CiteScore 1.3

[mdpi.com/journal/
religions](https://mdpi.com/journal/religions)

About the Journal

Message from the Editorial Board

Fresh developments in the disciplines that consistently make significant contributions to our understanding of religious personality, authority, devotion, and community – disciplines ranging from psychology, sociology, and anthropology to history, art history, philosophy, literary criticism, and political science – fuel general, as well as scholarly, interest in the world's religions.

Religions is inviting innovative and comparative contributions. Please consider Religions as an exceptional, exciting enterprise ready to reward your trust, attention, and participation.

Editors-in-Chief

Prof. Dr. Arndt Büssing

Professorship Quality of Life, Spirituality and Coping, Faculty of Health, Witten/Herdecke University, Gerhard-Kienle-Weg 4, 58313 Herdecke, Germany

Prof. Dr. Klaus Baumann

Caritaswissenschaft und Christliche Sozialarbeit, Theologische Fakultät, Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg, Platz der Universität 3, D-79098 Freiburg, Germany

Author Benefits

High Visibility:

indexed within Scopus, AHCI (Web of Science), ATLA Religion Database, Religious and Theological Abstracts, and other databases.

Journal Rank:

CiteScore - Q1 (Religious Studies)

Rapid Publication:

manuscripts are peer-reviewed and a first decision is provided to authors approximately 24.5 days after submission; acceptance to publication is undertaken in 4.9 days (median values for papers published in this journal in the second half of 2025).